

Efficient Composite Fabrication Using Electron-Beam Rapidly Cured Polymers Engineered for Several Manufacturing Processes

Thomas C. Walton, Aeroplas Corporation International, PO Box 7997,
Nashua, NH 03060-7997
James V. Crivello, Ph.D., Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Dept. of Chemistry,
Troy, NY

ABSTRACT

Specially formulated, low cost, efficiently processed, ultra high specific strength and stiff graphite fiber reinforced polymeric composite resins are of great interest to commercial transportation, construction and aerospace structure manufacturers for use in various components with enhanced degrees of weight reduction, corrosion/erosion resistance and fatigue resistance. 10 MeV Electron Beam cure processing has been found to increase the cure rate by an order of magnitude over thermally cured systems yet provide less molded in stresses and high T_g s. The physical properties and advantages of several newly developed resin formulations for a variety of composite manufacturing processes will be presented.

Figure 1. Simplified Schematic Of Several Composite Manufacturing Processes Suitable For E-Beam Curing

INTRODUCTION

Structural composites have already made, and will continue to make, a major impact on the aerospace and commercial industries. However, the mechanical and chemical properties of current materials used in the fabrication of composites are being stretched to the limits of their capabilities when applied to the hostile environment of space. This is particularly true of fiber reinforced organic polymer composites which undergo rapid erosion when exposed to atomic oxygen in low earth orbit (LEO). Further, organic resin composites often undergo outgassing on exposure to the high vacuum of space. This leads to contamination of critical surfaces of the structures surrounding the composite. Because of these deficiencies in present composites,

there is a need for novel materials specifically designed for long term use in a space, LEO or high altitude environments.

In addition to the above considerations, traditional composite fabrication techniques are slow, difficult and very costly. Further, the traditional lay-up and thermal cures result in composites with considerably less than the theoretical properties predicted for them. Novel means of fabrication which are faster, less costly, less complicated and result in reduced thermal stresses are being sought to alleviate these difficulties.

The objective of this Small Business Innovative Research (SBIR) program is to demonstrate the feasibility of an innovative, rapid, and cost-effective composite processing technique which effectively reduces the need for expensive tooling and autoclave processing and can cure the composite in seconds (compared to hours) at ambient conditions. The process is based on electron-beam curing of novel polymers that have been shown to resist atomic oxygen, while exhibiting satisfactory mechanical and physical properties as were summarized in the phase 1 work¹. These composites are designed to, in the low earth orbit space environment, to outperform composites produced by competing fabrication techniques .

Space structures also have both structural and environmental requirements. Today's state-of-the-art epoxy resin composites are desirable materials for use in space. However, they suffer like most polymers when exposed to the atomic oxygen flux of low earth orbit. Structures made using composites must be designed to last up to thirty years. It is well known that the current composite resins of choice degrade rapidly when exposed to atomic oxygen. It is highly desirable, therefore, to develop a rapid curing structural or other specialty composite resin that is not completely destroyed in an atomic oxygen flux environment. Self-healing characteristics or chemistries which occur with most polymers that preferentially leave a by-product that forms a protective barrier for the remaining composite material are of great interest.

A full characterization of a series of resins of this nature is necessary to determine if polymeric resins with this self-healing characteristic can truly function as structural composite matrix resins and coatings¹. For our study, we have chosen an epoxy resin control which is well known for its resin transfer molding processability. This resin is Dow Chemicals' TACTIX 123 thermally cured with a 25 pph resin H41 hardener. The recommended cure schedule for this composite resin system, that we followed, is one hour at 80°C followed by two hours at 150°C. Although the structural properties of this resin are excellent, the resin tends to be brittle.

There are many limitations of the current thermally cured resin systems. If a resin could cure in seconds or even minutes, rather than hours, it would change the way we think about the use and the manufacture of composite materials.

Also, in the last ten years, a large focus has been placed on the environmental and ecological dangers of certain types of industrial prepregging operations. Most of the epoxy prepreg resins as well as many other processing resins for that matter are processed using solvents such as acetone, MEK or other solvents. Use of this solvent-based prepreg process yields a high quality prepreg, but at great expense. Most prepreggers who process mainly solvent based prepreg usually have an afterburner to burn the solvents that are driven off to leave the prepreg at a low enough volatile content before use. It is desirable to stay away from these types of solvent processable resins in favor of a hot melt type prepreg or RTM resin systems in which no solvents are present during the raw material or composite fabrication process. Cure times for our resins engineered for electron beam irradiation curing are at least ten times faster than the most reactive current epoxy resin system. In addition, a variety of different

viscosity resins have been prepared which allow for tremendous versatility in the method of composite manufacturer, whether it be resin transfer molding, filament winding, pultrusion or plain vacuum bag lay-up. A variety of different manufacturing approaches would be possible if a wide viscosity range of resins were available. This is the aim of continually improved composite resin formulations specifically for this application developed by Aeroplas Corporation International. Typical applicable simplified E-Beam process schematics are shown in Fig. 1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

All electron beam irradiations were carried out using the I-10/50 Electron Linear Accelerator (I=Industrial; 10=10 MeV; 50=50 kW) as shown in Fig. 2, which is located at E-Beam Services, Cranbury, NJ. A scanning 10 MeV (electron energy) pulsed electron beam can scan a 16 to 31.5 inches wide path at the conveyor train car bed level. Fig. 2 shows a vertically mounted horn for the scanned pulsed electron beam. Two types of E-Beam cure characterization studies were carried out: the first was neat resin castings carried out in 1/16 inch thick aluminum faced molds set for a constant 1/8 inch neat resin thickness, and the other was vacuum assist RTM molded into 8H satin graphite or 7628 fiberglass fabric reinforced composites. The molds as seen immediately prior to cure can be seen in Fig. 3. The molds were cured riding over an aluminum rail car box to a nominal 80 KGy dose.

Figure 2 - Close Up Of The 50 kW Vertical Horn For The Scanning Electron Beam At E-Beam Services Where All Our High Dose Rate Electron Beam Cure Experiments Were Carried Out

Figure 3 - Shows Two 12 Inch Square Rtm Molds Filled With Aeroplas Resin And Graphite Fabric Preforms About To Be Irradiated (5 Neat Resin Casting Molds Also Shown)

Figure 4 - Shows The Dynamic Mechanical Properties In Rectangular 3-Point Flex, Dual Cantilever Mode For Aeroplas Ic-11C Atomic Oxygen Resistant Rtm Resin; Curve Shows Are E* Vs. T°C, E'' vs. T°C & Tan Delta Vs. T°C

Figure 5 - Shows The Dynamic Mechanical Properties In Rectangular 3-Point Flex, Dual Cantilever Mode For Low Cost Aeroplas FW-08 Filament Winding Or Pultrusion Resin; Curve Shows Are E^* VS. $T^\circ\text{C}$, E'' vs. $T^\circ\text{C}$ & $\text{Tan } \Delta$ Vs. $T^\circ\text{C}$. Note: Higher T_g For This Formula

E-BEAM CURING PROCEDURE

All curing took place behind thick concrete walls inside the accelerator room. Doses of approximately 50-80 kGy. were nominal.

COMPOSITE TEST PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

Six critical performance property tests were carried out on laminates with a level of priority established by how they performed on the most important mechanical property tests. The tests are as follows:

- Barcol impressor hardness (Model 934.1 at room temperature).
- Flexural strength and modulus (in accordance with ASTM D790 at room temp.)
- Tensile strength in modulus (in accordance with ASTM D638 at room temp.)
- In plane shear strength (in accordance with ASTM D3846).
- Dynamic mechanical properties (E' or G' ($E' = 3 \times G'$ for poisson's ratio very close to 0.5)² vs. temperature up to 400°C in accordance with ASTM D4065).

The control used for comparison in all our testing was the previously mentioned Dow TACTIX 123/H41 epoxy resin transfer molded using the same lot of carbon fiber fabric used on all the other test samples.

SUMMARY

The results in this characterization show that multi-processable, rapid E-Beam curable resins can be successfully formulated. Preliminary formulation dynamic mechanical properties are summarized in Figs. 4 and 5. One interesting thing to note is that the E* or flex modulus falls off for the AO resistant IC-11C resin after about 150°C whereas the FW-08 continues to hold up past 190°C. Summaries of the offgassing and preliminary UV-B exposure tests results are given in Table I.

The offgassing tests showing excellent low results for the IC-11 RTM version neat resin is 0.61 TML and 0.01 CVCM. Several resins were prepared by novel synthetic methods. It was shown that the viscosities of these materials can be controlled using several different approaches to give materials which are suitable for either resin transfer molding (65 cPs @ 25°C) or conventional hot melt prepreg fabrication (> 1,000,000 cPs at 25°C). These resins were fully characterized and then subjected to E-Beam and x-ray cure radiations. It was confirmed that the fiber filled resins display excellent reactivity toward both e-beam and x-ray irradiation under ambient or low temperature conditions which suggests less molded in stresses. The typical doses used to cure the resins were of the order of 50-80 KGy. It was observed that the presence of graphite fiber had a retarding effect on the cure but that the overall electron beam cure could be satisfactorily carried out in thick sections up to 12 inches thick with cure through full thickness or 12 inch thick sections have been laminated when curing in steps.

Structural composite-worthy properties were demonstrated with T_gs up past 190°C (something we never expected to find). Low outgassing and low susceptibility to moisture were also found for these relatively hydrophobic neat resins.

Composites with Spectra 900 polyethylene, E-Glass and graphite fiber reinforcement (all specially sized) were fabricated successfully with the IC-11 RTM resin. Data on several new formulas, not available at press time, will be presented.

BIOGRAPHY

Thomas C. Walton serves as a founder and president of Aeroplas Corporation International. Mr. Walton has been very successful in commercializing many novel polymer composite materials and high energy plasma thermal spray paint products. Mr. Walton holds a B.S. in Chemical Engineering with a minor in Nuclear Engineering from Northeastern University in Boston, MA and an M.S. in Plastics Engineering from the University of Lowell in Lowell, MA. He is the current Chairman of the Boston Chapter of SAMPE. Mr. Walton is also a member of the Society of Plastics Engineers (SPE), the American Institute of Chemical Engineers, and the American Chemical Society.

Dr. James V. Crivello is professor of Chemistry at Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute in Troy, NY, and holds a Ph.D. in Organic Chemistry from the University of Notre Dame. Dr. Crivello is a world renowned scientist with expertise in rad cure chemistry. His research interests include: organic oxidations and nitridations, synthetic arylation reactions, the synthesis of polyimides and block copolymers, design and synthesis of initiators for thermal, electro and photoinitiated cationic polymerization, Optical, electron-beam and x-ray lithography. Prior to joining RPI, Dr. Crivello was a member of General Electric Corporate Research and Development Center for over twenty years. He is a two time IR-100 Award

recipient (1973, 1978). Dr. Crivello is very widely published. He has authored over 108 Journal articles, 12 book chapters and is accredited with 96 U.S. Patents. Dr. Crivello is an active member of the American Chemical Society, ACS Professional Relations Committee, and Member at Large of "Polymer Materials Science and Engineering Division" of the ACS.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors acknowledge with thanks the following individuals, who without their guidance this work would not have been possible: Pranoti Bhatt and Thomas Stednick of E-Beam Services, Mr. Chris Saunders and Mr. Vince Lopata, Atomic Energy of Canada, Ltd. (AECL) and Dr. John W. Connell, NASA-LaRC.

Table I - Comparison Of The Cleanliness (Offgassing), Atomic Oxygen And Uv Radiation Resistance Of A State-Of-The-Art Graphite-Composite Matrix Resin (Ic 11)fj

POLYMER BINDER	COMMERCIAL NEAT 300°F CURED EPOXY RESIN	EPOXY FUNCTIONAL SILOXANE (IC-11)
PROPERTY		
Usefulness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commercially available • Long track record • Barely meets offgassing requirements in full composite form • No atomic oxygen resistance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low outgassing • Room temperature • No molded in stresses • Rapid E-Beam processing
Cleanliness; Outgassing (Astm E595)		
Total Mass Loss: (Tml) % Collected Volatile Condensable Material: (Cvcm) %	1.42 ¹	0.61
Water Vapor Recovered: (Wvr) %	0.05	0.01
	N/A	0.07
Atomic Oxygen Resistance Or Self Healing Characteristic	No Atomic Oxygen resistance	Plasma asher, 40 hour space shuttle ² and TEM ² exposure demonstrate self healing atomic oxygen resistant characteristics
Quantitative Uv Radiation Resistance Screening (Quv-Q Panel) (Uvb-313) Exposure For 240 Hours	Very poor UV resistance Darkens, breaks down	Slight Amber Color after exposure of neat resin film ³

¹ Extrapolated from graphite uni-prepreg test data @62% fiber volume (73% by wt.) .

² Complete report not available at press time from NASA LaRC.

³ This sample was: G1650-sc (a similar modified version of IC-11).

REFERENCES

1. Walton, T. C. and J. V. Crivello, "Innovative Composite Fabrication Using Electron-Beam Rapidly Cured, Micrometeoroid and Atomic Oxygen Resistant EFS Polymers", Proceedings of 39th Intl. SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition (1984).
2. Ferry, J.D., *Viscoelastic Properties of Polymers*, 3rd Edition, J. Wiley and Sons, P. 24 (1980).